

LABOVIAN EXPLORATION OF THE SECOND LANGUAGE TEACHERS' TEACHING – LEARNING LIVED EXPERIENCES AMIDST PANDEMIC

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 19

Issue 6

Pages: 296-706

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1791

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11115313

Manuscript Accepted: 04-20-2024

Labovian Exploration of the Second Language Teachers' Teaching-Learning Lived Experiences Amidst Pandemic

Alvin G. Butil*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This qualitative-phenomenological study presented the Labovian exploration of the lived experiences of second language teachers on teaching-learning and their guiding principle amidst the pandemic. The Labovian Conversational Narrative Model was employed in extracting the lived experiences of the teachers and analyzing the principles that emerged from their narratives. I used purposive sampling to select my participants who are the ten (10) second language teachers of Polomolok East District. I utilized interviews through the use of a validated in-depth interview guide. From their responses, it was found that the use of the Labovian Conversational Narrative Model was a great help to narrate the experiences and reflections of the participants. Moreover, the guiding principles of the teachers are being resilient and ICT competent, and prioritizing safety. This study may help other researchers by providing additional literature and references about the use of the model as their guide in getting the participants' narrative. This may also be a motivational drive to do future studies that may create a clear understanding of the model.

Keywords: *labovian exploration, lived experiences, teaching-learning*

Introduction

Educators are facing one of our greatest instructional challenges. They are thinking of ways to create meaningful and appropriate content that meets the needs of the students even when they are apart, to create a classroom experience for them though they are not in the physical space with us. Teachers cannot recreate the same experience; they must build an alternate experience (Brandon, 2020).

The unexpected pandemic interruptions to education have created a significance to research in documenting the major shifting in teaching practices, instructions, and tasks of the teachers. Different stories and daily teaching-learning experiences from the teachers were realized and reflected. I have decided to conduct a study on the lived experiences of the second language teachers amidst the pandemic and use the Labov's Conversational Narrative model as my framework in getting the stories of the teachers.

The use of narratives to express one's thoughts, beliefs, and worldview is very important. Since the middle of the nineteenth century, narrative has been "one of the central concerns of humanistic and social scientific philosophy." It is known as the "narrative turn" in various human sciences domains. It has been applied to numerous different disciplines, including criminology, technology, language and gender, psychiatry, and psychology. The focus on narrative analysis began with Aristotle, who established the fundamental elements of narrative plot in his book *Poetics* (Ferdig et al., 2020).

Hence, this study expanded the understanding of the Labov's Conversational Narrative Model. The narrator can easily share their stories when guided by the six components of the model: abstract, orientation, complicating action, evaluation, resolution, and coda. These elements are used as a framework to extract the narratives of the participants.

As I went through all the research about the experiences of second language teachers amidst the pandemic, the new educational system, teachers' challenges in teaching-learning and their coping mechanism as an intervention to the problem, I found out that various studies such as the study of Kim (2013) had been conducted recently. However, these studies do not use Labovian Theory as a lens in getting the narrative of the teachers.

As this research study gives and contributes information about teaching-learning experiences amidst the pandemic, this may provide additional literature and references about model and create understanding about the model. For educators, the COVID-19 pandemic is an exemplary adaptive and transformative challenge, one for which no advancement playbook can guide appropriate responses. With the use of the model, the second language participants demonstrated their daily teaching-learning experiences and personal narratives during the pandemic.

Research Questions

The study discussed the daily teaching-learning experiences of the second language teachers of Polomolok, East District amidst the pandemic utilizing the Labov's Conversational Narrative Model. Specifically, this study sought answers to the following questions:

1. How is Labov's Conversational Narrative Model demonstrated in the stories of the second language teachers' daily teaching-learning experiences during the pandemic?
2. How do these daily experiences serve as guiding principles to make teaching-learning effective even during the pandemic??

Literature Review

Labovian Conversational Narrative Model

Labov (1967) presents narratives that could be analyzed through the use of the Conversational Narrative Model. He separates the clauses based on how they served in the story in order to identify the fundamental structure. He has provided the most well-liked model of all, as was previously noted, for the organization of narrative clauses. His model is divided into six (6) components. It can be found in "completely constituted" narratives. Orientation (time, place, scenario, people), complicated action (the order of the events), assessment (the significance and meaning of the action as well as the narrator's attitude), resolution (things actually happened), and coda make up the elements of a summary (the perspective returning to the present).

Abstract. At the beginning of a narrative is an abstract operating as a summary of the story about to be told. This section of the plot of the story serves to both capture the listener's attention and explain why the story is being told. The abstract can sometimes include the entire idea of the story, but it can also be a free phrase that can be inserted anywhere in the narrative without changing the meaning of the statement from the participant (Labov, 1972). The narrative "The Lottery" by Shirley & Rusnalasari (2014) says that the story is about an annual rite known as "The Lottery." It also states that "the village people began to gather in the square, between the post office and the bank, around ten o'clock." This statement presents the abstract of the narrative. The reader's attention is captured by the opening line, which draws their curiosity about the reason behind the early morning gatherings. Hence, according to Berman (2014), the use of abstract in Narrative Analysis (NA) involves showing the aim of the participant in telling a story by summing up its relevance.

Orientation. Present at the beginning of a narrative is the orientation which serves to set up the story. Information regarding the "time, place, people, and their activity or circumstance" is provided during orientation. The orientation functions to present the background of the information, such as time, setting, participants, and circumstances. Orientation will provide the audience with enough information so that they can interpret the story (Labov, 1967). As Johnstone (2018) contends, orientation does not happen close to the opening of the story, in contrast to Toolan (2016), who links orientation with the environment by highlighting the narrative, context, and time of the participants.

Complicating Action. The main stage in a narrative is the mandatory complicating action that objectively depicts the events according to their chronological sequence. Complicating action clauses are narrative clauses that recapitulate a chronology of events leading up to their climax, the point of maximum suspense (Labov, 1972). The complicating action in a story refers to the actual events that drive the plot and keep the audience interested. The narrative phrases that make up the story's core answer the question, "And then what happened?" (Labov, 1972). This is typically the longest section of a story and it includes both orientation and assessment (Afsar, 2013).

Evaluation. It shows the importance of the story by including the narrator's attitude and further information. Evaluation explains the interest of the listener in the story by highlighting any intriguing or unique events. Its purpose is to clarify the thesis of the story. Evaluation can occasionally be found in the narrative's "two-part structure" (Labov, 1972). According to Afsar (2013), the evaluation itself may appear throughout the story within the comments of the speaker on the events. This may include many features that will be helpful for the audience to identify the points within the story.

Resolution. The climax of the story is resolved in the resolution stage. The conclusion or resolution reveals what actually transpired and releases the tension. It aids in understanding how the outcome transpired. The resolution of complex activities that follow the most notable episode constitutes a personal narrative's denouement, according to Labov (1972). The resolution or result alleviates pressure and answers the question, "What finally happened?" (Johnstone, 2018). It frequently starts with the last narrative sentence that describes how the complicated action was resolved.

Coda. The story will then be resolved using the coda. Coda is the mark of closure that may shift the time frame of the narrative. With coda, the audience will be able to grasp the storytelling present. The coda, which summarizes the conclusion of the story, comes after this section of a narrative. In addition to the aforementioned parts, appraisal is a crucial factor that might change at any time during the narrative. This component explains the narrator's motivation for telling the story (Labov, 1972). Toolan (2016) asserts that a coda signifies the conclusion of the narrative and makes it illogical and impossible to ask and it asserts that the narrator switches between the past and present of their narratives. Moreover, Johnstone (2018) stated that coda serves as a sort of link between the real world and the world of fiction.

Methodology

Research Design

In order to examine this study carefully, I used phenomenological-qualitative research design. Cresswell (2017) defined phenomenological research as an inquiry-based process of understanding a social or human problem and challenges based on building a complex holistic picture formed or output with words, presenting detailed views and opinions of participants and conducted in a natural setting and environment. I employed a variety of techniques for acquiring data, including observations, and structured or semi-structured interviews. I gathered the data from reliable sources to ensure credibility. I used Labov's Conversational Narrative Model as a guide in crafting the interview questions. Through the use of the model, the data was gathered from interviews with the second

language teachers; their daily thoughts and experiences during the pandemic were highlighted.

Participants

I used purposive sampling to select unique cases that are especially informative. The rationale for selecting this approach was to seek knowledge about the daily teaching-learning challenges of the second language teachers, which the participants would provide by virtue of their experiences. The ten (10) participants were Senior High School and Junior High School teachers of Polomolok East District who were second language teachers. The participants were composed of one (1) male teacher and nine (9) female teachers. Moreover, the participants were public school teachers with English teaching loads assigned in Polomolok National High School and Palkan National High School with permanent status in the Department of Education. I chose secondary language teachers because they teach a single subject while elementary educators teach all subjects in their school district curriculum. These participants have so much to share about their experiences, sentiments, excitement or something serious to discuss about their experiences in teaching-learning amidst the pandemic.

Instruments

I used an in-depth interview guide in extracting the narratives of the participants. Basically, this aided me in gathering data, organizing the research, and understanding the process and phenomena under study. It is essential to have firsthand experience with anything before being able to accurately describe it in writing. Additionally, even though the main questions were pre-planned, I employed a semi-structured framework.

Data Analysis

The recorded audio and video that I collected during the gathering of data using the in-depth interview were transcribed for thorough and absolute analysis. I used narrative and thematic analysis in interpreting the data to understand how the participant constructed narratives and stories from their own personal experiences.

I used the Labov's Conversational Narrative Model for lenient and accessible references when research questions posted in the study needed to be answered. This model demonstrated how verbal accounts of daily experiences of the participants scrutinized for the structural elements and functions. Most oral narratives of my participant were composed of clauses relating to the six components of abstract, orientation, complicating action, evaluation, resolution, and coda. Furthermore, in interpreting and analyzing the daily experiences that serve as guiding principles to make teaching-learning effective even during the pandemic, I used thematic analysis. I identified the core ideas using the narratives of the participants, and formulated the major themes and the frequency of their responses or the commonalities of responses from the narratives of the participant through a table.

Ethical Considerations

I ensured that all ethical considerations were followed as mandated by the Holy Trinity College of General Santos City because it helped to avoid engaging in practices which may implicitly or explicitly abuse or exploit those whom I sought to do research with.

Before I started my interview, I introduced myself to my participants to have an idea about the activity. I asked their permission to allow me to conduct an interview. I presented the consent and explained the things to be included in the study and manner of the interview. I put a lot of time and effort into getting to know my research study. I was aware that sometimes I interacted with people on a local level and that frequently when I did so, I learned intimate facts about people's lives. Significantly, research participants must feel at ease providing or disclosing personal information or bringing up contentious topics. With this, I respected the need for privacy in this situation.

Throughout every phase of my research, I took care to maintain the confidentiality of the research participants. I accomplished this by obtaining informed consent from research participants. Sex and gender bias refers to an insufficient representation of men and women in study samples. The inquiries made are in accordance with the comprehensive interview guide, which may have an impact on my own thought processes and biases. In several facets of the situation, I was more inclined to learn knowledge and spot potential complications. The data and the outcome impacted by the sex, gender, language, age, race, and marital status of the researcher. The outcome is influenced by how I present myself, including how I dress and behave. Knowing the native cultures of my participants helped me better comprehend and integrate into their way of life, which may affect how I approach my work.

Results and Discussion

The results of this study are discussed in this section. An overview of accounts of the participants are also presented to provide context for these findings. Then, based on the guide questions, the statements of the participants are presented in this part.

Labovian Conversation Narrative Model as Demonstrated in the Teaching-Learning Experiences of Second Language Teachers

In a nutshell, as TBS gave her narratives, she felt worried that they were not able to give the students a proper end to the school year. It was also actually hard to teach students without seeing them face to face. It really changed her daily routine but she was somehow

able to adjust to the new normal setup. Although she felt sad about the event, she was striving not to be disturbed by the circumstances. She always stood to her core as a teacher and was able to adapt to the change of time. She narrated:

“...I was worried that we were not able to give the students the proper end to our school, but then I think it's better not to get them back inside the school since, I mean, health is more important than anything else.”

However, TKZ wrapped up her narratives of being optimistic. She mentioned that teaching is not just a career, but it is her advocacy because she knew that many teachers gave up during that trying time. Many chose to venture to other professions, because the challenges in pandemic time are really hard. Of all the struggles she went through as a teacher, she always believes that there is a purpose of everything. She openly accepts the new normal situation and learns to adapt to the change of time.

“...As I said, teaching is a vocation. I do not know other works, but only teaching and sharing knowledge with the learners. I do not know what else to do in life. I always see myself as a teacher.”

In THL and TMC narratives, they said that as the facilitators of learning, teachers must adapt to the change of time by doing everything that they can in order for the learners to learn even in this time of pandemic. The use of different online platforms, especially the Group Chat (GC), needs to address their concerns. We have to think of our role as a teacher, since we are the facilitator of learning. We have to stand still in the test of time and keep to our promise that we have our learners in spite of our mission and vision. With their ideals and aspirations, these teachers exemplary stated their purpose of teaching. They tried to cope with their challenges even at their own level and share what they have learned. During our conversations, these teachers really showed how important their learners are to them. They are very emotional when they speak about their learners' challenges during the time of pandemic.

“...Yes, of course, but on the other side, sir, I am also concerned, and I am also thinking of my learners because, at this crucial time, this is the time that my learners need my knowledge and skills for them to also have that knowledge and skills of mine transferred to them.”

“...Yes, the noblest of all, because you're not just giving what you know; you also give what you have in your heart. Especially if you understand what you are calling when it comes to teachings.”

Orientation

There were ten (10) teachers who shared their stories based on their individual experiences amidst the pandemic. They are handling English subjects in the Junior High School and Senior High School department. These teachers shared many stories that made these narratives more interesting. With this number of years teaching young students, these teachers had a lot of experiences to share. During the pandemic, they dedicated their lives and professionalism in Polomolok National High School and Palkan National High School which are in Polomolok East District, Polomolok South Cotabato.

TBS is one of those ten (10) teachers who has a lot of experience in teaching amidst the pandemic including the changes in her daily routine as she had to adjust to the new school setup. She did not have any idea why there was a lockdown because she did not hear the news. She also thought that it would only be for a month or a week but then the school was closed for quite some time and they were not allowed to go back to school.

“...At first, I didn't have any idea why we were locked down because I hadn't heard of the news, but I was thinking that it would only be for a month or a week. Then, the school year had already ended, and we were still not allowed to get inside the school to go back to school.”

“...The nationwide lockdown due to the COVID-19 pandemic affected me greatly, especially my emotional, psychological, and mental health as a teacher. An abrupt change in our day-to-day routine was made, including canceling in-person classes and suspending academics and events across the different campuses nationwide.”

Complicating Action

The participants shared the problems during the pandemic especially in the teaching-learning. TBS revealed that the transition from classroom teaching to online instruction had been a huge challenge to all educators and even to the students. There were a lot of changes from face-to-face meeting to virtual meeting and from face recognition to online attendance. They knew it takes a while to adjust to a new normal however beyond the heartbreaking circumstances, teachers were all still learning to provide and sustain the needs of the students

“...The quality of education is the main issue facing the field of education. How can a pandemic be used to provide high-quality education?”

“...I think the major one of the major issues of teaching-learning is how students adapt to the new learning environment in the new learning process because until now, I have found I can see my students or my learners that they found it hard to answer the modules alone.”

“...Um, for me some major issues and teaching learning today is the health and safety of everyone. We're trying to be healthy and safe.”

No effect on the learners too because their parents are already jobless because of the pandemic. In school, we also lack equipment or toolkits to fight COVID-19.”

Moreover, TAC considered it as a major problem because COVID 19 pandemic has been continually devastating across the globe and it caused a huge change of the educational landscape in the country. The question remained on whether we were completely prepared to utilize those substitute means in providing education without compromising the quality of education among our students.

“...I consider it a major issue because the COVID-19 pandemic has been continually destroying across the globe, and it has caused a huge change in the educational landscape in our country.”

Apart from this, my study participants described the behavior of the students towards teaching and learning in the new school. Most of the teachers observed that the students had been lazy and dependent. Students procrastinate in answering their modules. They did not submit outputs on time.

“...Well, the student’s learning behavior is also poor. I would say it’s because students are getting lazy. They’re procrastinating in answering their modules. Let’s say, when you’re going to say the deadline is on this day, they are going to submit it two weeks later, or not at all. Some students are really up to the deadliest deadline; they will not be able to submit their modules.”

According to TRS, as what she saw on their outputs, they were really having a hard time in sentence construction. TBS also added that their language skill development had been really poor. Even those students who belonged to the academic track had poor outputs. One can really see that they needed their teachers in answering their module because they could not understand even the simplest instruction. She believed that language skill development had been really poor because of modular distance learning.

“...From what I’ve seen, on their outputs, they are having a hard time in construction but then it’s a work in progress.”

“...Their language skills development is really poor. The outputs that I’ve already shared, even those students who belong to the academic track, have poor outputs. You can see that they need teachers in answering their module, even the simplest instruction, they couldn’t understand.”

For TMG, an English teacher was expected to teach different micro skills that students need to develop such as reading skills, comprehension skills, writing skills and their speaking skills. The first three skills mentioned are not so much a worry but in terms of speaking skills, she said that it had been really a challenge. Moreover, TMN noticed that based on their performance, inability of the students to interact with others may have hampered their language development. Social interaction is really one way to develop their language skills. But then, they had no opportunities to express their ideas anymore and share their feelings with others. They had no chance for social and emotional learning. Their speaking and some other skills had not been really fully developed.

“...We are expected to teach them the different micro-skills that they need to develop, like, their reading skill, comprehension skills, writing skills, and speaking skills. Now, with those three, the reading, the comprehension, and the writing, it’s not so much a worry for me. But in terms of speaking skills, I am very sorry for them.”

“...based on their performance, their inability to interact with others may hamper language development among students or learners. You know, sir, interaction is one way. Social interaction of learners is one way to improve them and develop their language skills.”

TKZ emphasized that it should have been because in using modules, teachers could not measure language skills of the students. Teachers let their students write paragraphs especially when they required them to interpret a graph in their lesson. Teachers could not assure themselves whether the outputs were really the work of the students. Teachers could also observe the errors in grammar. The language skill specifically in speaking and writing are the problem in modular distance learning.

“...That’s the sad thing. It’s because in modular, we cannot measure their language skills in terms of speaking and in writing. When we let our students write paragraphs, especially when I let them interpret a graph in our lesson, I cannot assure myself that it’s their work, right?”

Apart from this, my study participants described the behavior of the students towards teaching and learning in the new school. Most of the teachers observed that the students had been lazy and dependent. Students procrastinate in answering their modules. They did not submit outputs on time. In addition to this, TAC said that the new school set up had a great impact in their learning process and some students during online classes are too lazy to study. They often woke up late and eventually missed their class. In the modular classes, students submitted their modules beyond the deadlines. They were not even serious with their studies.

“...Well! Students’ learning behavior is also poor. I would say it’s because students are getting lazy. They’re procrastinating in answering their modules, let’s say, when you’re going to say the deadline is on this day, they are going to submit it two weeks after, or not at all, some students are really up to the deadliest deadline. They will not be able to submit their module.”

“...The students’ behavior towards teaching, especially in the new school setup, has a great impact on their learning process and some students during online classes are too lazy to study. They wake up late in the scheduled time of their classes.”

THL made a statement that when it comes to the behavior of the students, it is a burden on their part in the new school set up of learning

because they were used to having face-to-face classes. The abrupt change to modular or distance learning affected their motivation. Moreover, TLM said that learners disliked reading and writing. They had gadgets so they just relied on whatever was available on the internet or in their gadgets. They did not read and write intensively.

Evaluation

TBS also mentioned that as teachers, they really value their profession. It was their passion to teach these children and to impart knowledge to them that compelled them to do their job as teachers. After all, they are really fascinated by their roles as teachers in the lives of their students.

"I am a multitasker", TRS said. "We are not just a teacher on purpose, but we're also a mother, a friend, a psychologist, and at some point, a doctor." He also mentioned that he chose this profession because he loved what he was doing to inspire others and give the best and also bring out the best of them. It was not only about teachers but also about students who may face challenges in the future.

TBS and TMC also mentioned that as teachers, they really value their profession. It was their passion to teach these children and to impart knowledge to them that compelled them to do their job as teachers. After all, they are really fascinated by their roles as teachers in the lives of their students.

Based on experiences of TMN in face-to-face classes, the interaction with her learners was clearly observed. She was able to follow up their development. She could easily get feedback about the progress of her learners. She was also able to spot her individual differences of the learners. In modular distance learning, she was not able to do it; hence, students could not produce quality output and it was really disappointing for her.

Resolution

Participant TBS also said that the role of the teacher never changes. It was very consistent and responsible not for them but also for the knowledge of values that would help them. She also mentioned that the role of the teacher was to inspire them to strive hard even if the setup is not really the same. Participant TLM also said that the role of the teacher never changes. It was very consistent and responsible not for them but also for the knowledge of values that would help them. She also mentioned that the role of the teacher was to inspire them to strive hard even if the setup is not really the same.

"...The role of the teacher never changes; it is very consistent, and I believe that as a teacher, we are responsible not only for their knowledge for the teaching of knowledge but also for teaching them values that would help them live outside, not just in the school and also help them be responsible and resilient at the same time the challenges that the pandemic has brought."

My participants also shared the actions they made to help students to cope with their challenges in such trying times. Teacher MN said that at that time, English language students probably were the hardest to learn. In order for students to cope with difficulties in English using distance learning, teachers had to ensure that the learning materials for the students were all available and that they could access technologies. They had spelling or pronunciation difficulties, which needed to be addressed. She encouraged them to use the language especially in their performance tasks and parallel assessments.

"...At this time, the English language is probably the hardest to learn. In this pandemic time, students can cope with difficulties in English using distance learning. We should ensure that the learning materials for the students are all available and they can access technologies."

In the case of TBS, she only used Messenger as a communication platform. She called and texted them. She also tried Google Classroom once but students found it difficult to answer using the platform since these students had difficulty in accessing the internet. So, they went back to Messenger.

"...Unfortunately, I only use Messenger. Sometimes, I call them and text them. I tried Google Classroom once but students found it difficult to answer using Google Classroom since these students have difficulty in accessing the internet. So, we went back to Messenger."

In research class, TKZ recalled that she conducted limited face to face consultation. She found it more effective than just letting her students face their module, understand it and let them create their work. They just lived with the virus and observed the health protocols.

"...Especially in research, I have what I call limited face-to-face consultation. I do that to my learners and that's part of my study. I found it more effective than just letting my students face their module and understand their module and let them create their work, whereas, sometimes it's hard to create something that we know will just be a waste."

As for TMG, they were instructed to answer the questions of the learners during the school time only, considering that the learners had their own work in Senior High School. She tried to be considerate even during their research defense. She woke up during that time. She answered their queries relative to the lessons provided they were expressed in English.

"...This sounds funny sometimes. However, here in school, we were instructed to answer our learners' questions during school time only. Considering that the learners have their work in Senior High School, yes, they are working, they are working in a company, they

are working with their relatives doing the domestic jobs. So, I just tried to be patient. I just tried to be considerate to them even during our panel o'clock 11 p.m. I am still awake during that time. So, I still answer their queries relative to our lessons provided they expressed it in English."

TAC also highlighted their actions to help students cope with their challenges during pandemic. She said that in her school, they had a Summer Reading Home Reading Program (SHARP). In this program, teachers visited the slow learners to teach them and also gave them some reading materials like reading books, magazines, etc.

Coda

TBS said that the role of the teacher never changes. It is very consistent and responsible not for them but also for the knowledge of values that would help them live outside not just in school that would help them be responsible and resilient at the same time with these challenges and changes that the pandemic brought. She thinks that the role of the teacher is to inspire them to strive hard even if the setup is not really the same.

"...The role of the teacher never changes; it is very consistent, and I believe that as a teacher, we are responsible not only for their knowledge for the teaching of knowledge but also for teaching them values that would help them live outside, not just in the school, that would help them be responsible and resilient at the same time with this kind of challenges and changes that the pandemic has brought."

Moreover, THL keeps motivated from time to time because she always sees that this is the time where learners need her the most. She does everything and adapts to the change of time. She prays to God that everything is fine as days go by during the pandemic. She saw herself worthy in the career she chose.

"...Okay, honestly, I keep motivated from time to time. This was the time that my learners needed me the most. So, I have to do everything; I have to adapt to the change of time. I could help them as much as I could."

Moreover, THL keeps motivated from time to time because she always sees that this is the time where learners need her the most. She does everything and adapts to the change of time. She prays to God that everything is fine as days go by during the pandemic. She saw herself worthy in the career she chose.

Participants discussed their roles and responsibilities as English teachers in addressing the challenges that students faced during this pandemic. Certain teachers asserted that their position is unchanging and that they serve as facilitators of learning. They believe that even though the environment is different, the job of the teacher is to inspire students to work hard.

Furthermore, the participants also shared on how they changed their outlook as result of the experiences they went through in teaching-learning amidst the pandemic. They imparted their motivations to keep teaching during this trying time and suggested pieces of advice to teachers who are struggling to keep up during the transition. Teacher MG said that this situation was sound's funny sometimes.

Hence, TRS said that he chose this profession because he loved what he was doing. To inspire others, he wanted to give his best and also to bring out the best in them. You could say that they were prepared in what they call life outside the premise of the four corners of the classroom. He also mentioned that he was thinking that teaching is not just a profession, but it is really a calling too.

TAC also mentioned that although we struggled a lot specially mentally, socially, physically, and financially during the pandemic. She continued to teach because of her students during this difficult time. In her opinion, a more significant factor plays by resilience of the students and willingness to try new approaches to support them, particularly during this pandemic. This is how she pushes herself to carry on teaching in spite of the difficulties she is having due to the pandemic.

Teachers offered guidance to colleagues who were finding it difficult to keep up during this shift. TMG advised us to persevere and maintain an optimistic outlook as we will overcome all obstacles. She emphasized the need for educators to remember their responsibilities to our students, our school, and the Department of Education as employee teachers.

According to TMN, teachers need to accept and concentrate on the things that they can control, who also counsel the students to maintain stable mental health. Teachers should serve as positive role models for our students because they are the people that students look up to and enjoy each day as it comes and not worry about the future because they truly have no idea what it will bring, so they should take things day by day. Teachers should keep their promise that in spite of mission and vision, students are the top most priority.

In this part, participants demonstrated their obligation as an English teacher to address the challenges that the students faced during the epidemic. They also emphasized the steps taken to assist students in overcoming challenges when learning English remotely. Hence, the responses of the participants reveal the conclusion as part of Labov's Narrative Conversational Model by Labov (1972).

Guiding Principles of the Teachers that Make Teaching-Learning Effective During the Pandemic

The participants shared their experiences during the pandemic. They have imparted their narratives as they faced the challenges in the teaching-learning. I analyzed their narratives and crafted themes. The table below presents the three (3) guiding principles that emerged from the teaching-learning experiences of the teachers amidst the pandemic. There were three principles that emerged based on their

narratives, to wit: resilience, Information Communication Technology (ICT) competence, and health and safety as the major themes. I present the core ideas based on the major themes and the frequency of response. The major themes serve as their guide in facing their challenges in the new educational system.

Table 1. *Guiding Principles of the Participants*

<i>Major Themes</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>	<i>Frequency of Responses</i>
Resilience	Teachers and Students Must Adjust to the Need and Change of Time	General
Information Communication Technology (ICT) Competence	Teachers Must be Knowledgeable in Facilitating Learning Through the Use of Technology	General
Safety and Emotional Health	The Teacher Must Value and Prioritize their Safety	General
	The Teacher Must Ensure the Provision of Emotional Health Support	General

Resilience

Resilience is one of the major themes that emerged from the daily experiences of the teachers that served as their guiding principle to make teaching-learning meaningful during the pandemic. Based on their narratives, being resilient is a key factor in facing the challenges amidst the pandemic. It is the willingness to adjust and adapt to address the need in this changing time especially in teaching the students.

Moreover, most aspects of their lives have changed as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, which could cause tension, anxiety, and terror. Resilience enabled them to endure and get through adversity. Resilience, however, is not something they possess from birth; rather, it develops over time as a result of interactions between their experiences. Because of this, every person reacts differently to stress and adversity, such as the COVID-19 pandemic. There was only one core idea in this major theme: Teachers and students must adjust to the need and change of time.

Teachers and Students Must Adjust to the Need and Change of Time. Based on their narratives, teachers and students must know how to adjust in these trying times. They must know how to manage themselves especially in dealing with different challenges in the new educational system. While teachers are deeply, passionately motivated to show up for their students and create a positive learning experience for them, many also feel deep concern for their safety. A lot of people were really worried about whether it was even safe to sit in the classroom wearing a mask or not wearing a mask. However, as teachers, they had to be resilient with the advent of the pandemic and capable of adjusting in this changing time.

Chang and Yano (2020) stated that public education and private institutions may have changed their means in teaching their learners. Teachers in both public and private need to find ways and solutions to connect to their students and transition to unfamiliar modes of teaching quickly. Moreover, based on the narratives of the participants, it shows the need to adjust and adapt during the pandemic. Additionally, other papers concentrate on experiences, inventions, and methods for handling remote teaching (Ferdig et al., 2020) as well as descriptions of how schools and stakeholders adapted to the new scenario created by the pandemic (Moorhouse, 2020).

"...Honestly, I keep motivated from time to time. This was the time that my learners needed me the most. So, I have to do everything; I have to adapt to the change of time. I could help them as much as I could."

"...We are teachers by profession, by career, and by advocacy. So, we will continue our roles and responsibilities, especially bringing education into place, even in the face of a pandemic. Because, as teachers, we must see to it that learning continues. For now, during the pandemic, I believe that even if I cannot give the whole cup, at least I can give the drops; they will not be thirsty for learning."

Participant THL believed that resilience and willingness to find new ways to support students, especially during the pandemic plays a greater role. This was how she motivated herself to continue teaching even though she was facing the challenges amidst the pandemic. Adjustment and adaptation are her keys to face the challenges in the changing time. TKZ also mentioned that since they are teachers by profession, career, and advocacy, therefore, they have to continue their roles and responsibilities. Even if she could not give the whole concept of her lesson, at least she had shared something in order not to stop the education of learners. Relatedly, TLM also made her statement about resiliency.

"...The role of the teacher never changes; it is very consistent, and I believe that as a teacher, we are responsible not only for their knowledge for the teaching of knowledge, but also for teaching them values that would help them live outside, not just in the school, that would help them be responsible and resilient at the same time with this kind of challenges and changes that the pandemic has brought."

Participant TLM also mentioned that in order to address the challenges in such trying times, it would be a help to the teachers to be responsible and resilient. A resilient teacher should bounce back from the challenges and adapt in the face of adversity.

Information Communication Technology (ICT) Competence

Teachers believe that technology can be an important tool to facilitate distance learning in the short term; however, it is essential to

understand that it is a temporary solution that can never replace classroom teaching and learning and the invaluable face-to-face interaction between the teacher and student and among students. Teachers must be knowledgeable in facilitating learning through the use of technology. TKZ mentioned the importance of technology in facilitating the learning of students.

“...I think teachers must learn and be competent at using technology. We are now using these gadgets to deliver information and learning to the students.”

Teachers Must Be Knowledgeable in Facilitating Learning Through the Use of Technology. Based on the narratives of the participants, the unplanned and rapid shift to online learning without training and with little preparation has illuminated many benefits despite some problems. Learning with ICT support can encourage more interactivity among students and provide opportunities that may not have been possible before. Teachers believed that the integration of ICT used in education certainly continues to accelerate and certainly essential for generations to come. TMN made a statement about the use of technology in teaching the English language.

“...At this time, the English language is probably the hardest to learn. In this pandemic time, so that students can cope with difficulties in English using distance learning, we should ensure that the learning materials for the students are all available and they can access technologies.”

Aside from the lack of preparedness of the teachers in implementing online learning with such a short transition period, TKZ also highlighted that a teacher must maintain their professional status. The perception of teachers in technology was the determining factor in teacher professionalization in incorporating technology. She also added that learning ICT is very beneficial for both teachers and students. Both must learn and adapt to the latest learning technology, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic. During distance learning, teachers gained a lot of experience and new strategies in delivering materials to achieve learning objectives.

Additionally, Chang and Yano (2020) stated that the school administrators and district executives had to figure out how to link students and teachers to the internet, supply computers and laptops, and increase food service. They also switched to holding meetings online. It is not well known or verified that closing schools will stop the spread of viruses. During the pandemic, the roles of the teachers evolved. Many instructors have trouble utilizing technology since they are limited to working from home, have lesson plans that are no longer suitable or sufficient, must quickly master new technologies, and are separated from their students. K–12 students must create and improve new learning and the use of technology in teaching.

Two of the biggest challenges to moving America’s schools in online teaching- learning was an insufficient number of digital devices for students, and millions of households’ lack of high-speed internet at home. Students from lower-income households are struggling and striving to complete online homework or even manage it because of their unstable family situations (Cano, 2020). Most especially, learners belonging to interior Sindh or Baluchistan areas do not have their own laptops and other devices. Moreover, lack of high-speed Internet in their areas and some places are major issues (Waqar, 2020). These cases entailed a number of critical challenges of which was the existence of inequalities and unfairness in the access of technological means (equipment and internet access) to make sure to have adequate online teaching to all children and youth (Bao, 2020).

I have learned their guiding principles or beliefs from the daily experiences as second-language teachers in order not to compromise learning. Teachers had their realization about their role and responsibility and that is to promote cooperative learning activities. For them, teachers and students must be competent in ICT-based skills to be used in distance learning. Teachers must be knowledgeable on the utilization of ICT-based strategies in teaching students.

Safety and Emotional Health

The participants also emphasized that the pandemic really affected their emotional health, well-being, safety and ability to bring their best to the classroom. They had experienced high levels of stress from the uncertainty around, especially their safety not to be infected by the virus. Two core ideas emerged from the daily experiences of the teachers, namely: the teacher must value and prioritize their safety and the teacher must ensure the provision of emotional health support.

The Teacher Must Value and Prioritize their Safety. Safety and well-being of the students, teachers and education support personnel must be the number one priority. Teaching is such an intensive job and teachers can greatly benefit from learning about practicing self-care. Self-care is all about taking care of health and ensuring that everything needs to thrive.

“...I still believe that health is wealth. Teachers must be healthy because they are the backbone of the school, so they must stay healthy.”

“...the government must prioritize the well-being of the teachers, especially their health and safety. Viruses are everywhere, so we must secure ourselves from them.”

The stress and anxiety of the teachers realized during the pandemic, a flammable combination that could result in burning them out and lead them to leave their jobs. It is more important than ever to support the teachers by looking after their safety. Caring for teachers is an important and significant part of the recovery and a consistent and sustainable education outlook of the future (Chang & Yano, 2020).

The Teacher Must Ensure the Provision of Emotional Health Support. The trauma associated with COVID-19 can be devastating to students and educators, as some might have lost a loved one or colleague. Thus, teachers must secure and maintain emotional health stability to teach the learners. The job of a teacher is intensive so they should promote healthy wellbeing to relieve stress from the work.

Studies demonstrate that valuing teachers, prioritizing their emotional health, growing their collective self-esteem, and comprehending a teacher's workload are key to achieving excellent student learning results (Chang & Yano, 2020).

"...the advice that I can share is: first, just keep maintaining mental health, because there are things that we can't control, and we have to accept that and focus on things that we can control. Since students look up to their teachers, we should be positive models for our learners."

"...I believe that the school administrators will provide programs for the teachers, especially in counseling, because some of them are experiencing trauma during the pandemic."

Caring for teachers is an important and significant part of the recovery from the pandemic and a consistent and sustainable education outlook of the future. Moreover, research shows that successful student learning outcomes begin with caring about teachers, prioritizing their mental health, developing their combined self-esteem, and understanding a teacher's workload (Chang & Yano, 2020).

Therefore, resilience, ICT competence, and safety and emotional health are the guiding principles that teachers must consider. To enable us to continue the teaching-learning process, these things should be prioritized. These may help them to uplift the education standards and the need in the new educational system.

The use of the Narrative Conversational Model of Labov as a framework in this study helped in getting the personal narratives of the teachers. It served as my basis in making the interview questions. Moreover, the model of Labov guided the participants in sharing their narratives from the start until the end of the conversation.

The responses of the participants helped to open the worldviews and reflections in facing the challenges in teaching-learning. Their experiences were significant to the world of teaching especially in understanding the situation amidst the pandemic. They may become bases for the school administrators and the teaching personnel to craft an intervention in helping to solve the challenges of the teachers.

These principles may help the teachers to keep motivated and determined to teach in times of pandemic. They gave inspiring words to allow the teachers to breathe and continue their work amidst the pandemic. Moreover, it gave them hope to sustain their passion in teaching.

Conclusion

The narrative model I used in the chosen narrative was explicated in detail in the analysis section. All six structures—abstract, orientation, complicated action, resolution, evaluation, and coda—are included in it. The model helped me to analyze such narrativization of the life story of the participants. It satisfied every condition listed in the Conversational Narrative Model of Labov for what constitutes an effective narrative.

With all the shared stories of difficulties and struggles encountered by the daily teaching-learning experience of the teachers, the participants created resolutions or last course of actions they made to resolve the problem and how my participants changed their outlook as the result of the experiences they went through in teaching-learning amidst the pandemic.

I have learned their guiding principles where teachers had their realization about their role and responsibility and that is to promote cooperative learning activities. Teachers and students must be competent in ICT-based skills to be used in distance learning and be knowledgeable on the utilization of ICT-based strategies in teaching students. They may enhance the resilience they need to take on this challenge by establishing a strong foundation in their love of learning, accepting problems, and learning lessons they can apply to a new day in the classroom.

Furthermore, the result of this study may help the learners to manage their school tasks, home activities, and time. This study may also help the learners in sharing their narratives, storytelling activities and other oral activities. Through the help of this model, learners may be able to share their feelings, thoughts and sentiments. They may easily outline their stories and conceive the things that they want to share with the use of the model.

On the other hand, as a researcher and at the same time as an English teacher, this study may help to understand the model and use it in getting the narratives of the participants. It easily grasps the stories following the format of the model. The result of the study will also benefit the future researchers in widening their understanding on the use of the model.

References

- Afsar, A. (2013). A discourse and linguistic approach to biblical and Qur'ānic narrative. *Islamic studies*, 45(4), 493-517.
- Bao, W. (2020). "COVID-19 and online teaching in higher education: A case study of Peking University." *Human behavior and*

emerging technologies 2 (2): 113–115. doi:10.1002/hbe2.191.

Berman, L. (2014). *Speaking through silence: Narratives, social conventions, and power in Java*, London: Oxford University Press.

Brandon, H. (2020). *Maintaining the middle school experience during COVID-19: Teaching and embracing an understanding of the developmental needs of students*. Association for Middle Level Education.

Cano, R. (2020). “Track California schools closed by climate disasters, says lawmaker. The times we’re living in’.” *California matters*.

Chang, C., & Yano. (2020). *How are countries addressing the Covid-19 challenges in education? A snapshot of policy measures*.

Creswell, J.W. (2017). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Merrill Pearson

Ferdig, Baumgartner, Hartshorne, Kaplan-Rakowski, & Mouza. (2020). *Teaching, technology, and teacher education during the COVID-19 pandemic: Stories from the field*. Association for the Advancement of Computing in Education (AACE). <https://www.learntechlib.org/p/216903/>.

Johnstone, B. (2018). *Discourse analysis and narrative: The handbook of discourse analysis*, pp. 635-649. Oxford: Blackwell Publishers

Kim, Y. (2013). *Constructing personal stories: The structure and functions of Korean EFL learners’ oral narratives*. Korea National University of Education.

Labov, W. (1967). *Narrative analysis: Oral versions of personal experience*. Essays on the verbal and visual arts. University of Washington Press. <https://www.ling.upenn.edu/~wlabov/Papers/FebOralNarPE.pdf>

Labov, W. (1972). *Language in the inner city: Studies in the black English vernacular*. Philadelphia, PA: University of Pennsylvania Press.

Labov, W. (1982). *Speech actions and reactions in personal narrative*. Georgetown University round table on language and linguistics by Deborah Tannen, 219-247. Washington DC: Georgetown University Press. https://repository.library.georgetown.edu/bitstream/handle/10822/555474/GURT_1981.pdf

Moorhouse, B. L. (2020). “Adaptations to a face-to-face initial teacher education course online due to the COVID-19 pandemic.”

Nunan, D., Bailey, K. M., & Heinle, H. (2019). CENGAGE learning, Boston USA, 496

Shirley, L., & Rusnalasari, Z. (2014). *The Lottery*. Creative short stories. Mankato, MN: Creative education

Toolan, M. (2016). *Narrative: A critical linguistic introduction*.

Waqar, K. (2020). *Going online: Lessons from the classroom*.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Alvin G. Butil

Holy Trinity College of General Santos City - Philippines